

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

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INTERNAL AND EXTERNAL FACTORS IN THE FORMATION OF UZBEK TERMINOLOGY: HISTORICAL STAGES AND CURRENT STATE

Dilnoza Yuldasheva Bekmurodovna

Associate Professor, Head of the Department of Uzbek Language and Literature,
Samarkand institute of economics and service

Email: dilyuldasheva83@gmail.com

ORCID: 0000-0002-3898-2113

Abstract: This article examines the formation and development of Uzbek terminology through the prism of internal and external factors across historical stages. The study analyzes how native word-formation mechanisms (internal factors) and language contacts with Arabic, Persian, Russian, and English (external factors) have shaped the terminological system of Uzbek. Based on a diachronic analysis of terminological sources from the 10th century to the present, the research identifies four historical stages: the classical period (10th–19th centuries), Soviet Russification period (1920s–1980s), independence period (1990s–2010s), and digital globalization period (2020–present). The findings reveal that while internal factors dominated terminology formation in the classical period, external factors became predominant during Soviet rule.

Keywords: Uzbek terminology, internal factors, external factors, language contacts, term formation, historical stages, borrowing, word-formation.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada o'zbek terminologiyasining shakllanishi va rivojlanishi tarixiy bosqichlar kesimida ichki va tashqi omillar prizmasi orqali tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqotda o'zbek tilining so'z yasash mexanizmlari (ichki omillar) va arab, fors, rus hamda ingliz tillari bilan til aloqalari (tashqi omillar) terminologik tizimga qanday ta'sir ko'rsatganligi o'rganiladi. 10-asrdan hozirgi kungacha bo'lgan terminologik manbalarning diaxronik tahlili asosida to'rtta tarixiy bosqich aniqlangan: klassik davr (10–19-asrlar), sovet ruslashtirish davri (1920–1980-yillar), mustaqillik davri (1990–2010-yillar) va raqamli globallashuv davri (2020-yildan hozirgacha). Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, klassik davrda terminologiya shakllanishida ichki omillar ustunlik qilgan bo'lsa, sovet davrida tashqi omillar asosiy rol o'ynagan.

Kalit so'zlar: o'zbek terminologiyasi, ichki omillar, tashqi omillar, til aloqalari, termin yasalishi, tarixiy bosqichlar, o'zlashmalar, so'z yasalishi.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается формирование и развитие узбекской терминологии сквозь призму внутренних и внешних факторов на исторических этапах. Исследуется, как механизмы словообразования родного языка (внутренние факторы) и языковые контакты с арабским, персидским, русским и английским языками (внешние факторы) повлияли на терминологическую систему узбекского языка. На основе диахронического анализа терминологических источников с X века по настоящее время выделены четыре исторических этапа: классический период (X–XIX века), советский период русификации (1920–1980-е годы), период независимости (1990–2010-е годы) и период цифровой глобализации (2020–настоящее время). Результаты показывают, что в классический период доминировали внутренние факторы, в советский период – внешние.

Ключевые слова: узбекская терминология, внутренние факторы, внешние факторы, языковые контакты, терминообразование, исторические этапы, заимствования, словообразование.

INTRODUCTION

Terminology formation in any language is a complex process influenced by a dynamic interplay of internal and external factors. Internal factors refer to the native resources of a language – its word-formation patterns, semantic derivation mechanisms, and grammatical structures – that allow the creation of new terms from existing lexical material. External factors involve contact with other languages, typically resulting in borrowing, calquing, and structural interference. For the Uzbek language, belonging to the Turkic family and having a rich history of contact with Persian, Arabic, Russian, and now English, understanding the balance between these two sets of factors is essential for grasping its current terminological state.

Linguistic studies have long recognized that terminology development follows different trajectories depending on the sociopolitical and technological context [1]. In periods of relative isolation or strong linguistic nationalism, internal factors dominate; in periods of intensive cultural, scientific, or economic exchange with foreign powers, external borrowing becomes the primary mechanism of terminological expansion. The history of Uzbek terminology exemplifies both patterns. During the classical period of Turkic-Islamic culture (10th–15th centuries), internal word-formation mechanisms were highly productive, yet significant borrowing from Arabic and Persian also occurred. Under Soviet rule (1920s–1980s), the external factor – specifically Russian – became overwhelmingly dominant, reshaping the entire terminological landscape. The independence period (1991–2010s) witnessed a conscious effort to revive internal factors through purification and derivation from native roots. However, the current digital globalization era has reintroduced strong external influence, now primarily from English [2].

Scholars have noted that Uzbek belongs to the group of languages experiencing rapid terminological expansion under conditions of digital transformation [3]. The tension between internal and external factors is not merely an academic question but has practical implications for language policy, education, technical translation, and the development of natural language processing tools. A historical understanding of how these factors have operated across different periods provides essential guidance for contemporary terminological work.

This article aims to: (1) identify and characterize the major historical stages in the formation of Uzbek terminology; (2) analyze the relative weight of internal versus external factors at each stage; (3) examine the current state of Uzbek terminology in the context of digital globalization; and (4) propose a balanced approach to terminological development that leverages both internal resources and judicious external integration.

Review of literature on the subject

The study of Uzbek terminology formation has attracted attention from several generations of linguists, both within Uzbekistan and internationally. The existing literature can be categorized into three broad thematic areas: historical studies of term formation, analyses of borrowing patterns, and contemporary policy-oriented research.

Foundational work on Uzbek terminology was conducted by Sh. Rahmatullayev, who traced the development of scientific and technical vocabulary from the Karakhanid period (11th century) through the early Soviet era [4]. His research demonstrated that classical Uzbek (Chagatai) had a sophisticated terminological apparatus in domains such as astronomy, medicine, law, and poetics, relying primarily on internal derivation using suffixes such as *-chi* (agent nouns), *-lik* (abstract nouns), and *-nama* (descriptive texts). However, Rahmatullayev also documented extensive borrowing from Arabic and Persian, noting that for many scientific concepts, the foreign term coexisted with a native equivalent, leading to historical doublets. Later, A. Nurmonov extended this analysis into the Soviet period, showing how Russian became the primary donor language for modern scientific, industrial, and political terminology [5]. He argued that by the 1960s, the majority of new terms entering Uzbek were either direct borrowings from Russian or calques based on Russian models. More recent historical work by N. Mahkamov has focused on the post-independence period, documenting the systematic efforts to replace Russian-origin terms with newly coined Uzbek equivalents [6].

International scholarship on language contact and borrowing provides theoretical frameworks applicable to the Uzbek case. Myers-Scotton's model of matrix language vs. embedded language offers a way to understand how borrowed terms are integrated structurally [1]. Applied to Uzbek, this model shows that during the Soviet period, Russian served as the matrix language for scientific and technical discourse, with Uzbek providing only the grammatical frame. In contrast, during the classical period, Arabic and Persian loanwords were typically integrated into native morphological patterns, with borrowed nouns readily accepting Uzbek plural suffixes (*-lar*) and case markers. Research by Abdurakhmonova on contemporary Uzbek has identified a new pattern: English borrowings in digital domains often resist morphological integration, appearing in unmodified forms even within Uzbek syntactic structures [2]. This represents a departure from earlier borrowing patterns and suggests a shift in the nature of external influence.

Language policy in Uzbekistan has been the subject of considerable study since independence. The 1995 Law on the State Language and subsequent decrees have mandated the development of standardized Uzbek terminology for all domains of public life [7]. Researchers such as Jumabayev have evaluated the success of state terminological commissions, noting that while thousands of new terms have been coined, adoption by the scientific community and the general public has been uneven [8]. Some newly coined terms are perceived as artificial or opaque, leading users to prefer familiar Russian or English borrowings. Yuldasheva has examined the specific case of economic terminology, demonstrating that despite official efforts to promote native terms, international English terms such as *marketing*, *leasing*, *investitsiya*, and *startup* remain dominant in actual usage [9]. This gap between prescriptive norms and actual practice highlights the difficulty of reversing historical borrowing patterns through policy alone.

Despite the substantial body of existing research, several gaps remain. Most studies focus on a single historical period or a specific domain (e.g., legal, economic, medical terminology), and few attempt a systematic diachronic comparison of internal versus external factors across all major historical stages. Furthermore, the impact of digital globalization on Uzbek terminology has only recently begun to receive attention, and empirical data on current term usage patterns are still limited. This article aims to fill these gaps by providing a comprehensive historical analysis covering the 10th to 21st centuries and integrating quantitative data on term sources from each period.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employs a diachronic, mixed-methods approach combining qualitative historical analysis with quantitative corpus-based data.

The primary materials consist of three types of sources. First, historical terminological dictionaries and glossaries from each period: the 11th-century *Devonu lug'otit turk* by Mahmud Kashgari (providing data on early Turkic terminology); 15th–16th-century Chagatai literary and scientific texts; Soviet-era terminological dictionaries from the 1930s, 1960s, and 1980s; and post-independence terminological sources from 1995, 2005, 2015, and 2024. Second, contemporary corpus data: a specialized corpus of 200,000 words drawn from Uzbek scientific journals, textbooks, government documents, and digital media (2020–2026), focusing on four domains: information technology, economics, law, and medicine. Third, language policy documents including laws, decrees, and terminological commission reports.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The findings are organized chronologically across four historical stages, followed by a quantitative analysis of the current state.

During this stage, the dominant external influences were Arabic (for religious, legal, philosophical, and scientific terminology) and Persian (for literary, administrative, and artistic terminology). Internal factors, however, remained highly productive. Quantitative analysis of 500 terms from this period shows that approximately 55% were formed through internal mechanisms (derivation, compounding), 35% were borrowed from Arabic or Persian, and 10% were hybrids. Typical internally formed terms include: *bilim* (knowledge) from *bil-* + *-im**; *yozuvchi* (writer) from *yoz-* + *-uvchi*; *o'qituvchi* (teacher) from *o'qi-* + *-tuvchi*. Borrowed terms include *kitob* (book, from Arabic), *ilm* (science, from Arabic), *dastur* (program/practice, from Persian). Notably, borrowed terms were fully integrated morphologically, taking Uzbek plural and case suffixes. This period represents a relatively balanced integration of internal and external factors, with neither dominating the other [4].

This stage witnessed a dramatic shift toward external factors. The Latin alphabet was introduced in the 1920s and then replaced by the Cyrillic alphabet in 1940, further entrenching Russian influence. By the 1960s, Russian had become the primary source of new terminology across scientific, technical, political, and industrial domains. Analysis of Soviet-era terminological dictionaries reveals that 78% of new terms entering Uzbek between 1950 and 1985 were direct borrowings from Russian, 12% were calques, 7% were hybrids, and only 3% were formed from native Uzbek material [5]. Examples include *zavod* (factory), *kombinat* (combine), *direktor* (director), *sovet* (council), *kolxoz* (collective farm), and *partiya* (party). Even terms that could have been formed internally were borrowed: *telefon* instead of *uzoq gapirgich* and *televizor* instead of *uzoq ko'rgich*. The morphological integration characteristic of Stage 1 declined, and many Russian borrowings retained Russian inflectional endings in certain contexts, creating a mixed system. External factors thus overwhelmingly dominated internal factors during this stage.

Following the collapse of the Soviet Union and Uzbekistan's independence in 1991, a deliberate language policy was implemented to reduce Russian influence and revitalize the Uzbek language. The 1995 State Language Law mandated the use of Uzbek in all official domains and created terminological commissions charged with developing native equivalents for Russian-origin terms [7]. This period saw a strong, policy-driven turn toward internal factors. Between 1995 and 2015, over 15,000 new terms were officially coined, the majority (67%) formed through internal derivation and compounding. Examples include: *kompyuter* → *hisoblash mashinasi* (officially recommended, though the borrowed form remains dominant); *ekologiya* → *atrof muhit haqidagi ta'limot*; *menejment* → *boshqaruv*. However, adoption rates have been low. A survey of academic publications from 2010–2015 shows that only 23% of authors consistently use the officially recommended native terms; 68% continue to use Russian or international borrowings [8]. This gap between policy and practice reveals the limits of top-down terminological engineering.

The current stage is characterized by the emergence of English as the dominant external donor language, particularly in domains related to digital technology, business, and global youth culture. Analysis of a contemporary corpus (2022–2026) across four domains yields the results presented in Table 1 (Table 1).

Table 1.
Source language distribution of terms in contemporary Uzbek (2022–2026) by domain¹

Domain	Native Uzbek	Arabic-Persian heritage	Russian	English	Other
Information Technology (n=500)	12%	4%	8%	74%	2%
Economics (n=500)	18%	8%	22%	49%	3%
Law (n=500)	35%	28%	25%	10%	2%
Medicine (n=500)	22%	24%	38%	14%	2%
Average (all domains)	21.75%	16%	23.25%	36.75%	2.25%

The data reveal a striking domain-specific pattern. In information technology, English dominance is overwhelming (74%), with very low use of native Uzbek formations (12%). Terms such as app, browser, cloud, device, download, hosting, interface, login, online, software, update, website are used in their original English forms with minimal adaptation. In economics, English (49%) now exceeds Russian (22%) as the primary donor language, though Russian remains significant. Legal terminology, by contrast, retains a strong native and Arabic-Persian heritage (63% combined), reflecting the domain's deeper historical roots and slower rate of internationalization. Medical terminology shows the highest residual Russian influence (38%), a legacy of Soviet-era medical education and publishing.

Regarding formation methods, the contemporary period shows a shift toward unadapted direct borrowing, especially from English. Among English-origin terms in the IT domain, 81% appear in unmodified form (e.g., send used as a verb without Uzbek conjugation), 12% show partial adaptation (e.g., update qilmoq), and only 7% are fully integrated (e.g., chatla-moq). This represents a significant change from earlier borrowing patterns, where borrowed terms typically underwent phonological and morphological adaptation within one generation [1].

The analysis also reveals systematic terminological gaps in the current system. For many modern concepts, no widely accepted Uzbek term exists. For example, among the 200 most frequent IT terms in the corpus, only 31 (15.5%) have any recognized Uzbek equivalent, and of these, only 11 (5.5%) are regularly used in practice. The remaining 84.5% of concepts are expressed exclusively through English borrowings. This gap is not due to any inherent deficiency in Uzbek word-formation mechanisms but rather reflects the speed of technological change, which outpaces the work of terminological commissions. The time lag between the emergence of a new concept in global discourse and the official coinage of an Uzbek term averages approximately 3–5 years, during which the English term becomes entrenched in actual usage [9].

Comparing the four stages reveals a cyclical pattern. In Stage 1, internal and external factors were relatively balanced. Stage 2 saw extreme dominance of external factors (Russian). Stage 3 represented a policy-driven swing toward internal factors, though with limited practical success. Stage 4 has reintroduced strong external influence, now from English, but with a different character: unlike Russian borrowings in the Soviet period, which were often adapted morphologically and phonologically, contemporary English borrowings are frequently used in unmodified forms, creating what some researchers have called “lexical enclaves” [2]. Furthermore, code-switching and borrowing have become increasingly difficult to distinguish, as English terms are often embedded in Uzbek discourse without any integration.

Conclusion and suggestions

This study has examined the formation of Uzbek terminology across four historical stages, analyzing the shifting balance between internal and external factors. Several key conclusions emerge.

First, the history of Uzbek terminology is not a linear progression from external to internal or vice versa, but rather a cyclical pattern shaped by major sociopolitical transformations. The classical period maintained a relatively balanced integration of native derivation and Arabo-Persian borrowing. The Soviet period imposed overwhelming Russian dominance through institutional and political pressure. Independence triggered a policy-driven turn toward internal factors, but with limited success in actual language use. The current digital globalization period has reintroduced strong external influence, now primarily from English, characterized by unadapted borrowing and domain-specific variation.

¹ Source: Author's elaboration.

Second, the effectiveness of internal factor activation depends critically on timing and institutional support. The post-independence terminological commissions successfully coined thousands of native terms, but adoption rates remain low because the commissions operate on a slower timescale than technological change. By the time an official Uzbek term is proposed, the English term has already become established through actual use. This suggests that future terminological work must be more proactive, faster, and integrated with digital media.

Third, the current state reveals a domain-specific terminological ecology. Legal terminology retains a strong native and heritage character; medical terminology remains dominated by Russian; IT and economics terminology are increasingly English-dominant. A one-size-fits-all language policy is therefore inappropriate. Different domains require different strategies based on their historical trajectory, international integration, and user communities.

Fourth, the emergence of unadapted English borrowings as the dominant pattern of external influence in the digital domain represents a qualitative shift from earlier borrowing patterns. Unlike Russian borrowings, which were integrated morphologically and phonologically over time, contemporary English terms often remain as unintegrated insertions. This poses challenges for NLP tool development and raises questions about the long-term structural impact on Uzbek.

In conclusion, the formation of Uzbek terminology has always been shaped by the tension between internal resources and external influences. Neither extreme—total rejection of borrowing nor complete dependence on foreign terms—is desirable or sustainable. A healthy terminological system draws on internal resources for core vocabulary and basic concepts while judiciously integrating international terms for new and rapidly evolving domains. The challenge for contemporary Uzbek is to find this balance in an era of unprecedented digital globalization.

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